

OFFICIAL BUSINESS STYLE IN MODERN COMMUNICATION

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ANNOTATION

This article reflects about official business style in modern communication and investigates the official business style which serves areas of activity designed to regulate relations between people, institutions, countries, between citizens and the state. Administrative, legal, diplomatic, military sub-styles are considered the main sub-styles of business style in the article. The functional features of the official business style are explained carefully with examples like objectivity, imperativeness, dryness, accuracy, impersonality, clarity, lack of imagery and emotionality. Researchers and students can get adequate information for their academic purposes in this article.

Key words: *business style, functional style, accuracy, impersonality, speech genre, functional component, expressive component, extralinguistic factor.*

In linguistics, there are many definitions of functional style, which are interpreted by different authors in different ways.

I.V. Arnold gives the following definition: “Functional styles are language subsystems, each of which has its own specific features in vocabulary, phraseology, syntactic constructions, and sometimes in phonetics. The emergence and existence of functional styles is due to the specific conditions of communication in different spheres of human activity” [Arnold, 2002, p. 384].

M.N. Kozhina, a leading specialist in the functional stylistics of the Russian language, believes that “functional style is a peculiar character of a speech or its other social variety, corresponding to a certain sphere of social activity and a correlative form of consciousness with it, created by the peculiarities of the functioning of language

means and specific speech in this area. “The organization that creates a certain general stylistic coloring” [Kozhina, 1983, p. 198].

D.E. Rosenthal, in accordance with the functions of the language, the following styles are distinguished: colloquial (communication function), scientific and official business (message function), journalistic and literary and artistic (impact function) [Rosenthal, 1968, p. 17].

Professor Brandes defines it as follows: “functional style is a functional system, a system of internal, hidden relations and connections of phenomena, in which the functions of purpose and impact of a literary work are manifested. Outside of this system, these functions of a speech work are not realized” [Brandes, 1990, p. 110].

Well-known Russian Anglist N.M. Razinkina, who is engaged in functional stylistics, defines functional style as “a set of texts, written and oral, characterized by a more or less definite target orientation and the presence of linguistic means (at various levels), for which special selection and specific processing are typical” [Razinkina, 1985, p. . 98].

All these numerous definitions are united, first of all, by taking into account the extralinguistic factor when highlighting functional styles. It is the goals and objectives of communication in a particular area of communication that determine the choice of language means.

Dictionaries give the following definition of functional style: “Functional style is a kind of literary language, due to the difference in the functions performed by the language in a certain area of communication. The concept of “functional style” is central, basic in the differential division of the literary language, a kind of reference point for such concepts correlative with style as substyle, speech genre, functional-style sphere. The compositional-speech structure of functional style texts (i.e. the totality of linguistic elements in their relationship to each other and to the compositional structure of texts that are most characteristic of a given variety of literary language) is determined by the communicative intentions of the text creators, communication conditions and other style-forming factors. The specificity of a particular functional style lies in the

peculiarities of correlation, methods and techniques of combination, combination of language means (which in other styles can be presented in other combinations), their specialized use" [Educational Dictionary of Stylistic Terms, 1999, p. 341]; based on the definition of the linguistic encyclopedic dictionary, the functional style is considered "as a kind of literary language, in which the language appears in one or another socially significant area of people's social speech practice and the features of which are determined by the peculiarities of communication in this area" [Linguistic Encyclopedic Dictionary, 1990, p. 87], since it is the situation and the sphere of communication that determine the definition of certain means of expression that are characteristic of a certain functional style.

In his article "Languages of communication and functional styles (in their relation to the text)" G.V. Vekshin defines style and functional style in particular. Style is not only a scientific term, but also one of the key cultural concepts. In this capacity, the idea of style is the property of a common language, nationwide cultural consciousness.

Among native speakers, there is an idea of style as a complex of special forms and principles of behavior specific to a person or a group in typical circumstances of communication. One cannot speak "in style" (they say "in language"), but one can use it, say "in style"; style is a form of "presentation" of language as meaning, its "presentation". Style cannot be non-alternative, it is not inherent in subjects and objects that do not make a choice or are not subject to it, and is always the result of creative processing or transformation of the source material [Dolinin, 1987, p. 303]. The closest synonym for the word style is manner. Essentially the same ideas underlie the linguistic understanding of the nature of style [Vekshin, 2002, p. 36].

One of the varieties of style is traditionally considered functional style. Its selection is due to two circumstances:

- 1) functional styles are styles that are characteristic of the entire language community, and not just individual native speakers or groups;
- 2) functional style - something that is associated with those areas and is realized in those areas of people's activity in which all carriers of culture are somehow involved.

In other words, functional in language is what is dictated by the applicability of speech not just to “certain”, but to typical, universal in nature circumstances of communication and communicative roles, addressed to those areas of life that concern everyone - everyday life (relations with loved ones), official and political activities (relations with authorities), scientific and cognitive activities (relations, in a broad sense, with nature), aesthetic and religious activities (art and faith as “relations with eternity”).

In our opinion, it is this definition of functional style that is the most complete and complex, where all possible extralinguistic factors are taken into account.

Functional styles are characterized by stylistic meaning and stylistic norm.

By "stylistic meaning" is meant the stylistic characteristic of a linguistic element, that additional stylistic information that is superimposed on its lexical and grammatical meaning [Anisimova, 1991, p. 58].

The functional component indicates the functional stylistic coloring of the language element, i.e. for its use in a particular area of communication. Here are some typical examples of the verb to go in German: to go (neutral) - to drag one’s feet (colloquial) - to shift (official business).

The normative component indicates the normative stylistic coloring of the language element - its relation to the literary norm. It is customary to distinguish six normative levels: pompous, refined, neutral, literary-colloquial, rude-colloquial [Rizel, 1975, p. nineteen].

Consider an example: to run away (neutral), to take to one’s heels (rough-colloquial), retreat (pompous), to absquatulate (literary-colloquial).

The expressive component indicates the emotional-expressive coloring of the linguistic element, its ability to express various emotional-expressive shades, to carry out the function of evaluation.

Some language elements have a stable emotional and expressive assessment, which is recorded in dictionaries. Others acquire evaluativeness depending on the situation of communication and the attitude of the speaker to the called object, phenomenon. If one of the components of the meaning is marked, the language unit has a positive stylistic value, if all three components are neutral, the language unit has a zero stylistic value.

The stylistic meaning assigned to a unit in the language system is considered as its absolute meaning. The stylistic meaning acquired by a unit in a particular context is contextual. The stylistic meaning of a language unit determines the scope of its use, its compatibility with other language units.

The unmotivated use of language units with different stylistic meanings in one statement can disrupt the style of speech or even break communication: the vice-president was gaping at the stage (instead of looking).

In a broad sense, stylistic norms are understood as the mandatory patterns of choice and organization of both stylistically neutral and stylistically marked language norms in integral systems of the way of expression and types of text in all communicative spheres without exception. We are talking about linguistic stylistic norms as a backbone (paradigmatic) codified set of lexical, grammatical and phonetic means of expression that are associated with a particular functional stylistic system. Stylistic norms, both in the narrow and broad sense, clearly show the change of time and, at the same time, the close connection of linguistic and non-linguistic factors. This case can be illustrated by the example of the use of a paraphrase for a first person singular noun, which is indicated by the speaker / writer [Riesel, 1975, p. 43].

Vocabulary, depending on whether it belongs to oral or written speech, is divided into:

1) stylistically undifferentiated vocabulary - i.e. words and expressions that are used and understood by native German speakers in all communicative areas and situations, and

2) stylistically differentiated vocabulary - i.e. words and expressions, the possibilities of using which are limited by certain internal and external linguistic factors.

Let's move on to the classification of functional styles in English. Note that scholars do not have a consensus on how to classify styles. In our opinion, the most accurate and adequate is the classification of styles set forth by Professor M.N. Brandes: official business style, style of science and technology, newspaper and journalistic style, style of everyday communication [Brandes, 2003, p. 36]. It is also worth noting the classification of Galperin's functional styles: scientific, colloquial, business, poetic, oratorical and journalistic [Galperin, 1958, p. 424].

Functional styles are very diverse, they solve different problems, function in different areas of activity and situations of communication, are characterized by their own distinctive features, and are formed by lexical, grammatical and syntactic means characteristic of each style. For example, the scientific style is characterized by the use of special and terminological vocabulary, graphic information, a clear definition of concepts and phenomena, strict logic and consistency of presentation, and complicated syntax. Business style is characterized by professional terminology, the accuracy of the definition of the expressions and words used, the clichéd language means. The main property of the newspaper-journalistic style is its informativeness and expressiveness. The main feature of colloquial speech is its ease, unpreparedness. It is characterized by lexical heterogeneity, the use of colloquial and colloquial words, simplified syntax, emotionally expressive appraisal, facial expressions, and gestures.

Among the book styles of speech, a special place is occupied by the official business style, which is characteristic of legal, administrative and social activities. For such a phenomenon as the culture of speech, the official business style is very important, because it is used to draw up documents and business papers related to state

tasks, court cases and diplomatic communication. It is characterized by isolation, the stability of many speech turns, specific vocabulary and special syntactic turns. Documents written in a formal business manner are compact and filled with clichés and language clichés. These are international treaties, state decrees and acts, legal laws and court rulings, various statutes and official correspondence, as well as other types of business papers that differ in accuracy of presentation and language standard [Shakirova, 2011].

The official business style serves areas of activity designed to regulate relations between people, institutions, countries, between citizens and the state. The main sub-styles of this style include: administrative, legal, diplomatic, military sub-style. Each style performs its specific tasks and functions and is characterized by its own distinctive features. The functional features of the official business style are as follows: objectivity, imperativeness, dryness, accuracy, impersonality, clarity, lack of imagery and emotionality. The official business style has the function of obligation and formality. The main speech genres of the official business style are:

- * government regulations, decrees, laws in the field of government activities;
- * diplomatic negotiations, memorandums, notes and protocols in the field of international relations;
- * regulations, codes in the field of jurisprudence;
- * trade and commercial agreements, commercial correspondence in trade and economics;
- * military charters, orders, instructions in the field of military life;
- * business correspondence, acts, minutes of meetings, orders, announcements in official institutions;
- * official written statements, reports, receipts, wills in the business life of an individual [Brandes, 2003, p. 39].

The official business style is implemented by the following linguistic means: modal verbs (would you be so kind, We should also be obliged), command verbs (I

insiste on,), promptings (we kindly ask you to, We request you to), impersonal constructions (Referring to our telephone conversation).

Typical lexical means of designing an official business style are as follows: functionally colored vocabulary (to distraint, to interrogate), terms and terminological phrases (terms of payment, to establish business relationships), stable turns and clichés (In reply to your letter dated), collective nouns (information), nouns expressing collective unity (nuclear weapons), verbal nouns (development), passive verbs, indefinite personal pronoun "man", clericalisms, "clerical" adverbs (relatively, rather).

Consider the characteristic features of the official business style of the English language, where there are 3 varieties - the style of official documents, the style of business correspondence (Business English), the style of legal documents. As a special kind of business speech in modern English, the language of military documents stands out: orders, charters, reports, etc. [Galperin, 1958, p. 431].

The purpose of each document, written in a formal business style, is to reach a certain agreement in matters of politics, trade, service offerings, and so on. Any document must ensure complete clarity of the essence of the issue, express the main conditions that both contracting parties undertake to comply with. Language functions are only communicative and voluntarily.

Letters of recommendation, resignation letters, reprimands, etc. are written in the language of business correspondence. The style of business correspondence is characterized by an abundance of stereotypical language units (clichés, clichés): I beg to inform you, with a view to, to expire, etc. Such phraseological combinations and separate words - terms can be found in reports, charters, laws, notes, and each area has its own specific terminology. For example, in business documents of a financial and economic nature, there are such terms as extra revenue; taxable capacities; liability to profit tax, etc. In diplomatic terminology: high contracting parties; to ratify an agreement; memorandum; pact; protectorate; extraterritorial status; plenipotentiary, etc. Legal documents often contain such terms and combinations as: The international court of justice; casting vote; judicial body; to deal with a case; summary procedure; a

body of judges; to hear a case; as laid down in; on the proposal of the court; recommendation of.

The diplomatic language is characterized by the use of a certain number of Latin and French words and expressions that have received a kind of terminological coloring in the language of diplomatic documents. The most common words and expressions are: *persona grata*; *persona nongrata*; *pro tempore*; *the quorum*; *conditio sine qua non*; *status quo*; *mutatis mutandis*, etc. Common to all varieties of business style is the presence of all kinds of abbreviations, abbreviations, compound words, etc. For example, M. P. (Member of Parliament); P.M. (Prime Minister); U.N. (United Nations); R&D (Research and Development); START (Strategic Arms Reduction Treaty).

As for the syntactic features of business speech, the most common of them are long sentences, extended periods with an extremely branched system of allied communication. Sometimes one sentence covers all the terms of the agreement that predetermine the relationship and that may arise as a result of the implementation of such a relationship. The complicated syntax of business documents is historically explainable. Connections between sentences reflect, as is known, real connections between the expressed concepts. This connection is especially clear in the presence of appropriate unions that determine the nature of the connection. The period was usually used when the connection between parts of the statement was interrupted. [Volskaya, 1966, p. 144]

In addition to being clichéd, the formal business style is characterized by terminology. In the process of term formation, two main trends are noted - the formation of abbreviations and the creation of terms-phrases (cash in hand, cash on delivery, on cash, prompt cash). Job titles - the head of the credit department, sales manager, production manager, CEO (Chief Executive Officer). Simple common sentences prevail - target or conditions. The length is not limited, there are often gerunds, infinitives, participles. Nominal attributive phrases dominate. There are many

component nominative groups (to force down price - bring down the price), predicative units in the passive voice.

I.R. Galperin notes that the main purpose of a business speech is to reach an agreement between two or more interested parties. This predetermines the characteristic features of the language of this style [Galperin, 1958, p. 433]. Among the features stand out:

- 1) specific terminology and phraseology;
- 2) traditional means of expression;
- 3) the presence of all kinds of abbreviations, abbreviations, compound words, etc.;
- 4) the use of words in the main subject-logical meanings;
- 5) lack of figurative means (metaphors, metonymy, etc.);
- 6) the use of emotionally colored vocabulary as formulas of appeal, symbols for requests, refusals, conclusions, etc.

Among the syntactic features of business speech I.R. Galperin singles out long sentences, extended periods with an extremely ramified system of allied communication. This is because the links between sentences reflect the real links between the expressed concepts.

Business correspondence, regardless of its purpose and level, must meet the following five requirements:

1. Clearness;
2. Brevity (conciseness);
3. Completeness (fullness) (completeness);
4. Courtesy (courtesy);
5. Literacy (language) (correctness).

It should be remembered that any letter is a message (appeal to) the respondent. If the latter does not understand its meaning, he will naturally not be able to respond to it correctly. In order to ensure the clarity and comprehensibility of the letter, you need to find the most appropriate words and expressions that reveal the essence of what you want to state. At the same time, not only words and expressions matter, but also

punctuation, the length of sentences, the construction (internal structure) of the sentence itself, where the word order also carries a semantic load, as well as the breakdown into paragraphs (paragraphs). It should be added that in business correspondence, sentences should be as short as possible. Although at the same time we must remember that a continuous set of short, chopped phrases produces an undesirable impression (the so-called staccato effect). The language and structure of the sentence must correspond to the intellectual and educational level of the addressee [Gavranek, 1967, p. 32].

Brevity (conciseness). As you know, a problem for any business person (businessman) is the lack of time and in this regard, he always welcomes everything that saves him both time and energy. In this regard, the best letter for a business person will be the one, when reading which he will quickly grasp its meaning [Izrailevich, 2003, p. 496]. Thus, the clarity of words and grammatical structure are complemented by conciseness (brevity) of the writing itself. Brevity implies the exclusion from the content of the letter of all minor details, repetitions and long turns of speech. And at the same time, one should not oversimplify the letter to the detriment of completeness, which can be interpreted as impoliteness and tactlessness. It is impossible to ignore the main facts relevant to the case, as well as all those expressions and turns that emphasize the courtesy, cordiality and goodwill of the writer.

Completeness (completeness). The completeness of the content of the letter should never be sacrificed for its brevity. All the main thoughts and considerations of the author should be stated in the letter. In order not to miss anything, before writing a letter, a sketch is made of those points that should be reflected in the message. After compiling a draft, it is checked once again whether everything that was supposed is reflected. If something has been forgotten, it is added additionally. Sometimes, in order not to violate the integrity and logical harmony of the letter, a post-scriptum (P.S.) is given, which provides additional information, including information that is not directly related to the content of the letter.

Courtesy (courtesy). Every self-respecting business organization (firm), seriously concerned about caring for its success, should show maximum cordiality and courtesy in personal contacts with individuals and companies (institutions, enterprises), since success begins with expressions of respect and respect for the client (business partner) affairs. However, one must also know the measure in this, remembering the rule "do not overdo it." Too importunate and lengthy expression of courtesy testifies to the weak taste of the speaker, even if he is sincere in his feelings.

The form of courtesy depends primarily on the content of the letter, i.e. on whether it is about benefit or disadvantage for the addressee. For example, in case of refusal from any enterprise (case), impossibility to fulfill someone's request (proposal), maximum restraint should be shown in expressing courtesy.

But in any case, under the most unpleasant circumstances, sarcasm and insults are not allowed in business letters.

Literacy. Literacy is a mandatory requirement for business (and in general for any) letters. What you should pay attention to:

1. grammar (grammar) - the correct construction of sentences in accordance with the norms of the language;
2. spelling (spelling);
3. uppercase (capital) letters (capitalization);
4. punctuation;
5. agreement (in Russian) - for example, according to an order, thanks to ... etc.
6. writing numbers (digits) - for example, numbers up to ten are written in words, numbers (over ten) - in numbers [Veselov, 1989, p. 26].

Summing up the above, we note that communication in the field of legal relations is intended to serve the implementation of the basic functions of law, which regulates relations between people, institutions, states, between citizens and the state. In order to embody the basic functions of law, official business speech bears the color of duty, it is accurate, has an impersonal, nominal character, and is standardized.

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